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Digitalisation in European regions: unravelling the impact of relatedness and complexity on digital technology adoption and productivity growth

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ABSTRACT

Digital technologies are the cornerstone of platform, knowledge, and network economies, driving the interconnectedness, innovation, and efficiency that define these economic models. Consequently, digitalisation has recently become a key policy objective for regional economies. This paper provides empirical evidence on how the adoption of new digital web technologies is shaped by previous regional digital capabilities. The analysis is based upon an economic complexity and relatedness framework using novel data on digital web technologies' adoption for 278 European NUTS-2 regions between the years 2000 and 2022. Results show that regions tend to adopt new digital web technologies when they already master related digital capabilities. This paper also shows how digital complexity is associated with labour productivity gains at the regional level. Conclusions shed light on how regions adopt digital web technologies and serve as a tool for policymakers.

KEYWORDS

Digitalisation; relatedness; economic complexity; productivity; European regions

JEL CLASSIFICATION

L86; O14; O33; R11

1. Introduction

Digitalisation stands out as a clear policy objective worldwide. From international bodies (IMF, WTO, World Bank, European Commission), to national, regional, and local authorities, digitalisation has been highlighted as a fundamental pillar of economic development strategies. Issues such as digital connectivity, digital skills, internet use, and the adoption of digital technologies in businesses and the public sector, are included in almost every single economic development policy nowadays.¹

In this sense, the literature has studied how regions benefit from digitalising their economies in terms of employment growth, productivity, and environmental performance, among others. However, even when these benefits of digitalisation have been

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¹See for example 'The digital future' from the IMF (2021), 'Digital technologies and trade' working topic from the WTO, 'Digital development' understanding poverty from the World Bank, and the 'Digital strategy' from the European Commission (2022).

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identified, there is not such a comprehensive framework to understand how regions adopt new digital web technologies over time (Haefner and Sternberg 2020). This paper inquires about the evolution of digital web technology adoption for 278 European NUTS-2 regions between the years 2000 and 2022. It relies upon an economic complexity and relatedness framework to understand the importance of previous regional digital capabilities shaping the adoption of new digital web technologies. This framework has been previously used as a conceptual and analytical approach to understand how regions diversify in the production of new activities, industries, or technologies. This paper argues that the adoption of digital web technologies by regions; thus, digitalisation, is influenced by the existing digital capabilities regions already have.

Therefore, it is, to the best of our knowledge, the first time in which an economic complexity and relatedness framework of regional diversification has been applied to digitalisation, understood as the adoption of new digital web technologies. Previous literature on regional diversification has been more focused on the production of digital technologies rather than its adoption (Castellacci, Consoli, and Santoalha 2020; Diodato et al. 2023; Xiao and Boschma 2023). For such purpose, this paper also exploits a new source of data, the digital web technologies used to build firms' webpages. It uses the application programming interface (API) *BuiltWith* to check whether a certain digital web technology has been used, or is still being used, in firms' web pages. Results show how the adoption of digital web technologies is influenced by the previous digital capabilities that regions already have. Indeed, regions tend to adopt new digital web technologies when they are already specialised in related digital web technologies.

Moreover, this paper explores the correlation between the adoption of complex digital web technologies and labour productivity at the regional level. Once digital connectivity is largely ensured in Europe, regional differences in productivity can be linked with the adoption of complex digital web technologies rather than from access to the internet (Juhász et al. 2024). Results show that, indeed, regional digital complexity is positively associated with productivity gains at the regional level.

Therefore, the contributions of this paper to the literature are several. First, it shows how economic complexity and relatedness metrics can be applied to promote digitalisation policies. Digitalisation policies should consider the existing digital capabilities of regions when investing and promoting the adoption of new and more complex digital web technologies. While much of the previous literature in the field has been concerned with the ability of regions to diversify in the production of new technologies and economic activities, this paper focused on the adoption of digital web technologies, rather than its production. Second, by exploiting a new source of publicly available data, the digital web technologies used for building web pages, it opens new venues for empirically analysing digitalisation (Ashouri et al. 2024; Mazzoni, Pinelli, and Riccaboni 2024). This data allows to understand the regional dynamics in the adoption of digital web technologies rather than the creation of new digital web technologies, that may be better captured using patent data. Third, it shows how differences in the use and adoption of complex digital web technologies are correlated with labour productivity heterogeneity across European regions.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. [Section 2](#) explores the different strands of literature that converge in this issue. [Section 3](#) explains the data and metrics

applied for the analysis. [Section 4](#) discusses the empirical strategies. [Section 5](#) presents the main results. [Section 6](#) concludes and discusses policy implications and future research.

2. Regional digitalisation dynamics

The increasing importance of digitalisation and its inclusion in development strategies across territories have attracted the attention of scholars with very different backgrounds. The digitalisation literature has benefited from different approaches coming from several disciplines. In this sense, several benefits from digitalisation have been identified using different approaches, from management (Rêgo et al. 2021), environmental sciences (Bechtis et al. 2017; Chauhan, Parida, and Dhir 2022), innovation studies (Cho et al. 2023; Evangelista, Guerrieri, and Meliciani 2014), geography (Ash, Kitchin, and Leszczynski 2018), and economics (Tranos, Kitsos, and Ortega-Argilés 2021), among others.

While there is a common understanding of what digitalisation means across these fields, it is far from clear which is the best way to measure it. It is possible to define digitalisation as the transformation of socioeconomic systems due to the adoption of digital technologies (Katz et al., 2014). To measure digitalisation several approaches have been undertaken by the literature. Digitalisation has been proxied using data on hardware, broadband connectivity, digital skills of employees, internet users, and webpages, among others. In this sense, Wheeler and O’Kelly (1999) used the topology of internet’s hardware to study the spatial organisation of the commercial Internet backbone. Haller and Lyons (2015) used broadband speed to study business performance. Tranos, Reggiani, and Nijkamp (2013) used the internet’s infrastructure networks. Blank, Graham, and Calvino (2018) used the distribution of users in the UK. Tranos, Kitsos, and Ortega-Argilés (2021) used the number of firms’ webpages to study the long-run effects of early adoption of internet-related technologies on the productivity of regions in the UK.

Traditionally, the main issue with digitalisation was internet access. Regions focused on building networks to access the internet while ensuring a good quality in terms of speed. This first stage of digitalisation was named as the first-level digital divide (Blank, Graham, and Calvino 2018). Subsequently, the focus was not mainly on internet access, but on the emerging digital differentiation (Hargittai 2002), the usage gap (van Dijk 2006) or the participation gap (Jenkins et al. 2006). Once internet access was guaranteed in a large part of Europe, the issue shifted towards how to use and benefit from that access. This turnover also received the name of the second-level digital divide (Blank, Graham, and Calvino 2018).

This second-level digital divide is still present nowadays in regions across Europe. Although a large majority of firms have a digital presence on the internet, very few extract all the potential benefits. This heterogeneity may come from the kind of digital web technologies they use to build their web pages. Not every web page includes all the same tools and allows to perform the same tasks. While some technologies may be key to promoting e-commerce such as online payment or digital advertisement, others may just display information about commercial schedules and contact information (Elia et al. 2021). This is particularly relevant in urban contexts where there is an emergent digital divide in relation to the concept of smart cities (Caragliu and Del Bo 2023).

Therefore, to benefit from digitalisation, regions are trying to catch up in the adoption of digital web technologies. However, the adoption of new technologies is not a simple process. There is a strong path-dependency in which regions cannot just adopt the most complex available technology (Cohen and Levinthal 1990). This path-dependency implies that the future adoption of digital web technologies across regions depends on the existing capabilities such regions have in those technologies. Furthermore, digital capabilities are unevenly distributed across regions, resulting in a digital gap in terms of digital web use (Hargittai 2002; Jenkins et al. 2006; van Dijk 2006). Indeed, the role of existing local digital capabilities may be considered a crucial factor in explaining the diffusion and adoption of digital web technologies.

Drawn from the literature on knowledge diffusion and technological change, such as Bresnahan and Trajtenberg (1995), it has been argued that internet or web-related inventions fall under the category of general purpose technologies, so it is easy to absorb. However, more recently, Papagiannidis et al. (2015) argued that these web-related technologies are far more complex, in the sense that they are more difficult to understand, absorb, and use. The diffusion process of digital web technologies has an inherent spatial dimension and industrial heterogeneity (Brakman and van Marrewijk 2008; Gaspar and Glaeser 1998; Malecki 2002; Tranos, Reggiani, and Nijkamp 2013). This is supported by the research on the geography of innovation (Audretsch and Feldman 2004; Feldman 1994), highlighting that the diffusion of digital web technologies is inevitably linked to the geography of digital economic activities.

The existence of previous related digital capabilities in a certain region could facilitate the future adoption of new digital web technologies. This is directly linked with the notion of absorptive capacity, thus, with the easiness for a certain region to acknowledge, absorb, and adopt new methods, ideas and technologies (Cohen and Levinthal 1990). In this sense, Siachou, Vrontis, and Trichina (2021) propose a framework to highlight the role of absorptive capacity in influencing the digitalisation processes of organisations.

This concept is also linked with the notions of path dependence and the so-called principle of relatedness (Hidalgo et al. 2018). This principle of relatedness builds upon the notion of related variety (Frenken, Van Oort, and Verburg 2007), understood as the closeness between two economic activities. Therefore, regions tend to diversify into related, and not into unrelated, products (Hidalgo et al. 2007), industries (Neffke, Henning, and Boschma 2011; Xiao, Boschma, and Andersson 2018), technologies (Balland et al. 2019; Boschma, Balland, and Kogler 2015), and occupations (Farinha et al. 2019), among others. This does not diminish the importance of unrelated variety, which can also play a role in diversification dynamics, particularly for breakthrough innovations (Boschma et al. 2023; Castaldi, Frenken, and Los 2015; Frenken, Van Oort, and Verburg 2007). In this vein, the adoption of digital web technologies is also expected to follow this logic. Regions would have more chances of adopting new digital technologies when they already master related web technologies. Thus, the role of regional digital capabilities is crucial to understand the future evolution of digital web technologies' adoption. This leads to formulate the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis 1: Regions are more likely to adopt new digital web technologies that are related to the ones in which they are already specialised.

These differences in the adoption of digital web technologies for building web pages may be linked with regional heterogeneities regarding productivity gains from digitalisation. In such a digital world in which internet access is not anymore an issue for developed countries, what may matter is to use the most complex technologies to extract all the potential benefits. Complex technologies are usually characterised by requiring a high degree of knowledge recombination, being difficult to replicate and thus providing higher economic benefits (Fleming and Sorenson 2001; Hidalgo and Hausmann 2009; Mewes and Broekel 2022; Pintar and Scherngell 2020; D. L. Rigby et al. 2022). Thus, following the previous literature in the field, this calls for shifting the focus from the access to the use of digital web technologies. Indeed, there is a growing literature highlighting the rising importance of the so-called digital service economy and its implications for regional economic development (Capello and Lenzi 2021; Capello, Lenzi, and Panzera 2023).

It is then important to highlight that this increasing importance of digitalisation in policy agendas is due to the large potential benefits that digitalisation may bring to the regions (Haefner and Sternberg 2020; Tranos, Kitsos, and Ortega-Argilés 2021). Moriset and Malecki (2009) found that businesses tend to localise in areas with good digital access, reducing unemployment in these areas. Indeed, current debates on depopulation pointed out that digital access is a priority to retain the population in rural areas (Pontones-Rosa, Pérez-Morote, and Santos-Peñalver 2021). In this sense, Tranos and Ioannides (2020) argue that the adoption of ICTs offsets agglomeration benefits leading to spatial decentralisation.

Nevertheless, recently digitalisation has been accused of the opposite, of creating unemployment due to the incentives for offshoring. Even when the rise of ICTs has helped to foster the spatial fragmentation of economic activities, its effects on regional labour markets are not clear. In this sense, van Slageren, Herrmann, and Frenken (2022) argue that usually, the easiness to access new non-boundaries labour markets is exaggerated. They found that the impact of the gig economy, which is highly fuelled by digitalisation, on labour markets in the EU is not as relevant as expected due to the importance of geographical and linguistic barriers. Digitalisation requires skilled workers that may come from the same regional labour market, creating also demand spillovers towards less skilled occupations, generating more overall local employment (Moretti 2012).

Moreover, digitalisation is associated with several other benefits for regions. Krom, Piscicelli, and Frenken (2022) defend that the rise of online platforms may facilitate industrial symbiosis, contributing to the reuse of assets within industrial processes, and fostering the circular economy. In this sense, Nham and Ha (2022) point out that this relationship between digitalisation and circularity is nonlinear. Batabyal and Nijkamp (2016) argue that creative regions may benefit from the use of digital technologies when combined with innovation policies, giving rise to partial knowledge spillovers. Burgess, Parish, and Alcock (2011) find that the presence of regional tourism organisations on the internet can be a source of marketing and e-commerce for regions.

In any case, independently of the data source chosen for the empirical analysis, previous research has shown that there is a strong positive relationship between digitalisation and productivity. Najarzadeh, Rahimzadeh, and Reed (2014) also found a positive relationship between the internet and labour productivity. At the

firm level, Bloom, Sadun, and Van Reenen (2012) found a causal relationship between the use of information technologies on firm performance and productivity. Bertschek, Cerquera, and Klein (2013) explored the effects of broadband internet on firm performance. Abbasiharofteh et al. (2023) show that the intensity and quality of firms' hyperlinks are strongly associated with the innovation capabilities of firms. At the regional level, Tranos, Kitsos, and Ortega-Argilés (2021) found that there are long-run productivity gains derived from the early adoption of internet-related technologies at a regional level using web pages data. Mack and Faggian (2013) studied the link between broadband provisions and productivity for US counties, founding a positive relationship. Jung and López-Bazo (2019) found similar results for Brazil.

Furthermore, since the main issue of today's digitalisation is not mainly the internet access but the use of the available digital tools, the heterogeneity in the adoption of digital web technologies may be responsible for regional differences in productivity. This may be crucial considering that firms in the technological frontier are usually new and young firms (Belitski, Caiazza, and Lehmann 2021). As shown by Audretsch and Kerlbach (2004), startup firms increase the diversity of regional knowledge, facilitating the transformation of knowledge into exploitable or economically useful knowledge. In a similar vein, Fritsch and Mueller (2004) explore the role of new business formation on regional development. These new and highly innovative startup firms are the mechanism through which regions achieve labour productivity growth.

In a digital world, the use and adoption of digital web technologies are one of the main drivers of this enhancement of productivity. In this sense, Sahut, Iandoli and Teulon (2021) explore the so-called digital entrepreneurship phenomenon, and Sussan and Acs (2017) introduced a framework to understand entrepreneurship in the digital age. Lisa, Ibrahim, and Borges (2020) highlight the importance of digitalisation for startups' success, and Acs et al. (2021) provide a conceptual framework integrating the concepts of digital technology infrastructure, multisided digital platforms, and platform-based ecosystems.

Nevertheless, it is not always clear how to identify new and powerful digital web technologies. New does not always mean better. The literature on economic complexity has provided different tools to assess the complexity of technologies and the regions using them (Balland and Rigby 2017; Balland et al. 2019; Boschma, Balland, and Kogler 2015). Economic complexity metrics are based on the concepts of diversity and ubiquity (Hidalgo and Hausmann 2009). Thus, a region may be considered as complex if it is specialised in several digital web technologies, so it is diversified, and among the technologies in which it is specialised, there are digital web technologies in which not a lot of regions are specialised, so the technology is not ubiquitous (Balland and Rigby 2017).

These economic complexity metrics have been previously computed relying on different sources of data such as exports (Hidalgo and Hausmann 2009), patents (Balland and Rigby 2017; Balland et al. 2019; Boschma, Balland, and Kogler 2015), and value-added (Koch, 2021), among others. In a similar vein, by considering the number of highly innovative firms using each kind of digital web technology, a measure of digital complexity can be obtained, as explained in the following sections.

Hypothesis 2: The digital complexity of regions is expected to be positively associated with labour productivity gains at the regional level.

Therefore, there may be several channels through which complex digital web technologies may enhance productivity. For example, adoption of technologies such as *hosting* provide access to new markets, expanding the potential demand for the firms. Also, technologies such as *online payment* allows consumers to pay for their purchases directly through the web page, making lower transaction costs. Further insides from these digital web technologies are provided in the next section.

3. Data and variables

3.1. Data

As discussed in previous sections, there is no unique way of measuring digitalisation. In this respect, the literature has used different data sources in previous research such as the number of internet hardware or digital equipment, the number of internet users, broadband connectivity and access to internet, and the number of webpages, among others. This paper exploits a finer and more nuanced data source, which is the adoption of digital web technologies for building web pages. The adoption of digital web technologies across web pages is traced using the *BuiltWith* API (BuiltWith 2022). The *BuiltWith* API provides information on when was the first and last time a certain digital web technology was used in a certain webpage.²

These digital web technologies cover a wide range of functions, from basic programmes such as advertisement or analytics, to more complex such as online payment or e-commerce. In this regard, simple web pages might have basic digital technologies that just allow the web page to run and show its content. However, more sophisticated web pages may have more complex digital web technologies on top of the basic ones, such as online payment services, and fraud prevention, among others.

Since the large majority of firms may have simple web pages, most web pages in a region may look quite similar. However, for web pages powered by firms in the knowledge frontier, such as highly innovative firms and high-growth potential startups, this may be different. It is by adopting the newest and more complex digital web technologies how these companies may stand out in terms of performance, as previously discussed. This competition and variation in the adoption of digital web technologies is what needs to be captured to measure the digital complexity of territories.

Therefore, to identify these companies, this paper relies upon the CrunchBase dataset. The CrunchBase dataset includes information on high-growth potential startups and highly innovative firms (Dalle, Den Besten, and Menon 2017; Leendertse, Schrijvers, and Stam 2022). CrunchBase includes, among other pieces of information, the website of these firms, their location, and several other variables such as firms' age, ownership, and capital. The web pages of these companies were introduced into the *BuiltWith* API, so we could identify in which time periods each company was using a certain kind of digital web technology.

²For a detailed list of the considered digital web technologies, check [Annex I](#).

Moreover, using geocoding techniques, firms were located across European NUTS-2 regions.³ This geocoding was based on the addresses of the firms, as included in the CrunchBase dataset. Then, the data were aggregated at the regional level, obtaining the number of firms using each digital web technology by region and year. Using the addresses of firms implies certain bias towards headquarters' locations. However, due to the nature and characteristics of firms in CrunchBase, and their further regionalisation at NUTS-2 level, this limitation should be alleviated. Also, this headquarter bias, if in place, would translate into an underestimation of the capabilities in digital web technologies for some non-headquarter regions, thus positioning our analysis in a conservative estimation. The final number of digital web technologies considered for the analysis is 218.

This information was transformed into the matrix form required to compute the economic complexity and relatedness metrics. It consists of an $r \times i$ matrix with regions as rows (r) and digital web technologies as columns (i). This matrix is filled in with the number of firms using each kind of digital web technology in each region at that particular time period. For the purpose of the analysis, 8 non-overlapping time windows were considered: 2000–2002, 2003–2005, 2006–2008, 2009–2011, 2012–2014, 2015–2017, 2018–2020, and 2021–2022.

Finally, the measure of labour productivity on NUTS-2 level was derived using gross value added and total employment data from Eurostat. Data for the control variables at a regional level, namely GDP per capita, total population, and population density, were retrieved from Eurostat publicly available databases. To control for innovation dynamics, patent applications at the regional level were retrieved from the OECD REGPAT database. Data for UK regions were retrieved from the UK Office for National Statistics and the OECD.

3.2. Digital complexity

In order to derive the economic complexity and relatedness metrics, the starting point is the above defined $r \times i$ matrix. Combining information on both, which regions use specific digital web technologies (diversity), and how common specific digital web technologies are across regions (ubiquity), the digital complexity of regions can be measured. Empirically, this metric is obtained following the method of reflections, pioneered by Hidalgo and Hausmann (2009), and using the Knowledge Complexity Index (KCI) function from the *EconGeo* R package (Balland 2017). The KCI is computed through the application of the eigenvector reformulation of the above-mentioned method of reflections (Balland and Rigby 2017).

This method considers the regions that are significant users of digital web technologies. Thus, the previous $r \times i$ matrix is operationalised into an $r \times i$ two-mode matrix ($M = M_{r,i}$), where $M_{r,i}$ states whether or not a region r has a revealed comparative advantage (RCA) in the use of the digital web technology i . The RCA measure was previously used to determine the relative advantage or specialisation of a region, country, or firm in a particular product or technology compared to

³For a detailed list of the considered European regions, check [Annex II](#).

others. This RCA takes the form of a location quotient or Balassa index, in which a region r has an RCA in the use of the digital web technology i at time t if the share of firms using digital web technology i in the region is higher than the share of firms using the digital web technology i in Europe as a whole. This can be mathematically formulated as follows:

$$RCA_{r,i}^t = 1 \text{ if } \frac{Firms_{r,i}^t / \sum_i Firms_{r,i}^t}{\sum_r Firms_{r,i}^t / \sum_r \sum_i Firms_{r,i}^t} \geq 1 \quad (1)$$

$$RCA_{r,i}^t = 0 \text{ if } \frac{Firms_{r,i}^t / \sum_i Firms_{r,i}^t}{\sum_r Firms_{r,i}^t / \sum_r \sum_i Firms_{r,i}^t} < 1 \quad (2)$$

As previously stated, the method of reflections combines the diversity of regions and the ubiquity of the digital web technologies (Hidalgo and Hausmann 2009). These two variables are defined as the two-mode degree centrality of regions ($K_{r,0}$) and digital web technologies ($K_{i,0}$) in the region – digital web technologies network. These two variables can be formulated in the following way:

$$Diversity = K_{r,0} = \sum_i M_{r,i} \quad (3)$$

$$Ubiquity = K_{i,0} = \sum_r M_{r,i} \quad (4)$$

The diversity of regions and the ubiquity of digital web technologies are given by the number of digital web technologies in which a region has an RCA, and the number of regions that exhibit an RCA in that particular digital web technology, respectively. Both metrics, diversity, and ubiquity, are sequentially combined over a series of n iterations using the formulation provided by Hidalgo and Hausmann (2009):

$$KCI_r = K_{r,n} = \frac{1}{K_{r,0}} \sum_i M_{r,i} K_{i,n-1} \quad (5)$$

$$KCI_i = K_{i,n} = \frac{1}{K_{i,0}} \sum_r M_{r,i} K_{r,n-1} \quad (6)$$

Therefore, empirically, both the binary two-mode matrix M and its transpose M^T , are row standardised. Thus, by taking the product between both of them ($B = M * M^T$), which is a square matrix, the KCI for each region (KCI_r) is given by the second eigenvector of this matrix B . Notice that by reversing the product ($D = M^T * M$), the second eigenvector will give the KCI for each digital web technology (KCI_i) in this case (Balland and Rigby 2017). For the purpose of the empirical analysis, we use only the KCI_r , that we standardise between 0 and 100 to be comparable across time periods. Figure 1 shows the average digital complexity for the European regions between the years 2000 and 2022.

Figure 1. Average digital complexity for European regions between the years 2000 and 2022. Source: Authors' own elaboration.

3.3. Digital relatedness

Digital relatedness density measures how closely related are different digital technologies within a specific region based on their co-occurrence. The computation of the digital relatedness density follows a two-step process (Balland et al. 2019; Boschma, Balland, and Kogler 2015; Hidalgo et al. 2007). First, the relatedness between digital web technologies (ϕ) is obtained throughout a co-occurrence analysis. The data is divided into sum-matrices for the above-mentioned non-overlapping 8 time windows (2000–2002, 2003–2005, 2006–2008, 2009–2011, 2012–2014, 2015–2017, 2018–2020, and 2021–2022), with regions (r) in the rows and digital web technologies (i) in columns. The degree of relatedness (ϕ) is obtained applying a standardized method (Steijn, 2021), based on Van Eck and Waltman (2009), and using the *EconGeo* R package (Balland, 2017).

This measure of relatedness between digital web technologies can be used to map the digital web technologies' space. As previously done in the literature for products (Hidalgo et al. 2007), industries (Neffke, Henning, and Boschma 2011; Xiao, Boschma, and Andersson 2018), technologies (Balland et al. 2019; Boschma, Balland, and Kogler 2015), and occupations (Farinha et al. 2019), the following network shows how digital

Figure 2. Digital web technologies' space. Source: Authors' own elaboration.

web technologies are related between each other, based on the above-mentioned co-occurrence analysis.

In [Figure 2](#), each node represents a digital web technology. The size of each node reflects the eigenvector centrality of that digital web technology. It can be observed that digital web technologies related to analytics, content management systems (CMS), hosting, and shopping, are the most central ones in the network. Furthermore, the colours of the nodes show the technology groups.

Several implications can be derived from [Figure 2](#). In the first place, the above-mentioned central digital web technologies remain crucial to unlock new possibilities for diversifying in the adoption of digital web technologies. This contrasts with the fact that other technologies are much more peripheral in this process. For example, advertising and widget digital web technologies form clusters, being highly related across them but quite disconnected from the rest. Therefore, targeting central technologies in this space, can provide a better understanding of what technologies can provide access to new technologies.

In the second place, although some nodes for hosting technologies (green) remain central, others are clustered in the periphery. Thus, even within certain digital web technologies, some specific functions are much more important than others. Such differentiation on these features can help to identify what technologies can provide higher opportunities for future adoption and diversification. Finally, it is interesting to observe that the core of the digital web technologies' space is formed by technologies that act as the backbone of websites, such as analytics or CMS, rather than particular technologies offering specific functions, such as payment or shipping. Building capabilities around these core technologies could provide higher chances of future technology's adoption, although other peripheral

niches such as sales or digital trade services can still bring economic benefits (Stojkoski et al. 2024).

Second, the relatedness density is obtained for each region r and digital web technology i at time t by adding all the relatedness values of the digital web technologies that are related to digital web technology i_j , and in which region r has an RCA higher or equal to 1. This can be mathematically formulated as follows:

$$\text{Relatedness Density}_{r,i,t} = \frac{\sum_i x_{r,i,t} \phi_{ij,i_g,t}}{\sum_i \phi_{ij,i_g,t}} \quad (7)$$

Parameter $x_{r,i,t}$ is a dummy variable taking value 1 when the RCA of a digital web technology i in region r at time t is higher or equal to 1, and 0 otherwise. The relatedness density is calculated for each region and digital web technology for the 8 considered time windows using the *EconGeo* R package (Balland 2017). Figure 3 shows the average relatedness density for the European regions between the years 2000 and 2022.

Figure 3. Average relatedness density for European regions between the years 2000 and 2022. Source: Authors' own elaboration.

3.4. Labour productivity

Finally, this paper also explores the potential regional labour productivity gains that may be derived from adopting more complex digital web technologies. In order to empirically test whether the digital complexity of regions is positively associated with productivity gains, the following measure of labour productivity is used:

$$\log\left(\frac{GVA}{E}\right)_{r,t} \quad (8)$$

Where *GVA* is the gross value added and *E* is the total number of employees in each region (*r*) at time (*t*). This metric captures the labour productivity of regions by approximating it as the value created by employees per region and time period (Cardona, Kretschmer, and Strobel 2013). Following previous literature in the field, labour productivity is preferred over other productivity measures due to its computational easiness, and applicability to countries, regions, and industries (Tranos, Kitsos, and Ortega-Argilés 2021). Figure 4 shows the correlation between the average digital

Figure 4. Average digital complexity and average labour productivity for European regions between the years 2000 and 2022. Source: Authors' own elaboration.

Table 1. Summary statistics.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Entry	367,484	0.105	0.306	0	1
Relatedness density	384,751	26.424	15.457	0	100
Digital complexity	2,273	44.68	22.46	0	100
Log (Productivity)	2,384	10.76	0.707	7.765	15.95
GDP per capita	2,524	25,687	17,449	101.0	210,964
Total population	2,567	1,832,000	1,580,000	25,830	15,630,000
Total employment	2,451	766,252	698,011	0	6,653,000
GVA	2,630	39,820,000,000	51,260,000,000	0	705,800,000,000
Population density	2,202	429.9	1,127	2.100	11,509
Patents applications	2,076	192.1	504.2	0.167	6,507

complexity and the average labour productivity for the European regions between 2000 and 2022.

Finally, [Table 1](#) includes the summary statistics of the variables included in the empirical analysis. Notice that these variables are all at the regional level except for the entry and relatedness density which are at the region – digital web technology level.

4. Empirical framework

This section presents the identification strategies followed in the empirical analysis. Since the purpose of this paper is twofold, two different specifications are required. First, this paper studies how, based on their previous digital capabilities, regions adopt new digital web technologies over time. In this sense, the dependent variable is a dummy variable indicating the specialisation (*entry*) of a region r in a new digital web technology i . This variable takes value 1 when a certain region r acquires an RCA higher or equal than 1 in a certain digital technology i in which it was not specialised in the previous period $t-1$, and 0 otherwise. The main variable of interest is the relatedness density of the region with respect to that specific digital web technology. The following model can be formulated:

$$Entry_{r,i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 * Relatedness\ Density_{r,i,t-1} + \theta * X_{r,t-1} + \delta_{r,i} + \varphi_t + \varepsilon_{r,i,t} \quad (9)$$

This is a two-way (region-technology and time) fixed effects linear probability model (LPM) in which $X_{r,t-1}$ stands for a vector of control variables at a regional level, $\delta_{r,i}$ and φ_t for region-technology and time fixed effects, respectively, and $\varepsilon_{r,i,t}$ for the regression residual. Following previous literature in the field, linear probability models are preferred over logit and probit specifications since they may lead to bias or inconsistency when they estimate the model with a large number of dummy variables (Boschma, Minondo, and Navarro 2013; Greene 2012; Xiao, Boschma, and Andersson 2018).⁴ Following previous studies, control variables include GDP per capita, as a proxy for regional level of economic development, total population, as a proxy for population size, gross value added, as a proxy for regional economy size, total employment, as a proxy for the intensity in the use of labour, population density, as a proxy for agglomeration externalities, and patent applications, as a proxy for regional technological capacity (Balland et al. 2019; Barbieri and Consoli 2019; Neffke, Henning, and Boschma 2011). To control for an excess of kurtosis, these control variables are in logarithmic form. Since errors are

⁴The same results were obtained using logit and probit models. For further details, check [Annex III.](#) and [Annex VI.](#)

correlated within regions, standard errors are clustered at the regional level. Notice that to alleviate some endogeneity issues, all independent variables are lagged by one period and mean centred.

Second, this paper explores the potential productivity gains that may arise from acquiring higher digital complexity. In this sense, the above-explained labour productivity measure is used as a dependent variable. The main variable of interest is in this case the digital complexity of regions (KCI_r). The model is estimated as an OLS including two-way (region and time) fixed effects. This model takes the following mathematical form:

$$\log\left(\frac{GVA}{E}\right)_{r,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 * Digital\ Complexity_{r,t-1} + \theta * X_{r,t-1} + \delta_r + \varphi_t + \varepsilon_{r,t} \quad (10)$$

As in the first specification, $X_{r,t-1}$ stands for a vector of control variables at a regional level including GDP per capita, total population, population density, and patent applications, δ_r and φ_t for region and time fixed effects, respectively, and $\varepsilon_{r,t}$ for the regression residual. Control variables are included in logarithmic form to avoid excess kurtosis. Again, since errors are correlated within regions, standard errors are clustered at the regional level. To alleviate some endogeneity issues all independent variables are lagged by one period and mean centred.

5. Results

This section discusses the main results obtained from the above-explained empirical models. In the first place, results in [Table 2](#) show how the adoption of new digital technologies is positively and significantly influenced by the previous digital capabilities of regions. In this vein, regions tend to adopt new digital web technologies related to the ones they already master. The probability of adopting a new digital web technology is higher when regions are already specialised in related digital web technologies.

This positive and significant effect is also strong. An increase of 1 standard deviation in the digital relatedness density of a region is associated with a 6 percentage points increase in the probability of entry.⁵ It is important to underline that the unconditional probability of entry is around 11%, so the effect of an increase in the relatedness density is important. This result is in line with previous literature in the field covering general technological diversification (Balland 2016; Balland et al. 2019; Boschma, Balland, and Kogler 2015; D. Rigby 2015). While these previous studies focused on technology creation using patent data, in this case, results refer to technology adoption. It is then possible to state that the previous digital capabilities of regions matter for the future adoption of new digital web technologies.

In the second place, [Table 3](#) displays the results for the second empirical model. In this sense, the digital complexity of regions is, as expected, positively and statistically significantly associated with labour productivity gains. The adoption of more complex digital web technologies is associated with higher levels of labour productivity at the regional level.⁶

⁵The unconditional probability of entry is around 11%, as shown in the summary statistics in [Table 1](#). An increase by 1 standard deviation in the relatedness density will be associated with 6 percentage points increase in the probability of entry $(0.00389 \times 15.457) * 100 = 6.01\%$.

⁶A spatial econometric model was also applied, as shown in annex VI.

Table 2. Entry models (LPM).

	LPM – Dependent variable: Entry (= 1)			
	(1) Baseline	(2) Controls	(3) Full model	(4) Full model FEs
Constant	0.154*** (0.00121)	0.140*** (0.00185)	0.154*** (0.00131)	0.0515*** (0.00756)
Relatedness density	0.00352*** (0.000107)		0.00379*** (0.000118)	0.00389*** (0.000163)
GDP pc (log)		0.230** (0.102)	–0.163** (0.0814)	–0.0697 (0.154)
Total population (log)		0.203** (0.100)	–0.142* (0.0815)	–0.757*** (0.197)
GVA (log)		–0.215** (0.100)	0.133* (0.0801)	0.0905 (0.151)
Total employment (log)		0.0177 (0.0144)	–0.00950 (0.00941)	–0.0163 (0.0308)
Population density (log)		0.00589*** (0.00199)	0.00212 (0.00139)	0.621*** (0.161)
Patent applications (log)		0.000512 (0.00174)	0.0112*** (0.00133)	0.00287 (0.00346)
Observations	218,268	218,268	218,268	218,268
R-squared	0.017	0.002	0.018	0.053
Region-Tech FEs	NO	NO	NO	YES
Year FEs	NO	NO	NO	YES

All independent variables are mean centred and lagged by one period. Heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors (clustered at the regional level) are shown in parentheses. Coefficients are statistically significant at the * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$ and *** $p < 0.01$ level.

Table 3. Productivity models.

	OLS – Dependent variable: log(GVA/E)		
	(1) Baseline	(2) Controls	(3) Full model FEs
Constant	10.78*** (0.0299)	10.78*** (0.00708)	10.73*** (0.00844)
Digital complexity	0.00249*** (0.000908)		0.000310** (0.000143)
GDP pc (log)		0.850*** (0.0210)	0.672*** (0.0208)
Total population (log)		0.0485*** (0.0159)	0.989*** (0.241)
Population density (log)		–0.0370*** (0.00813)	–1.048*** (0.243)
Patent applications (log)		–0.0120* (0.00706)	0.0101 (0.00733)
Observations	1,783	1,783	1,783
R-squared	0.009	0.938	0.893
Region FEs	NO	NO	YES
Year FEs	NO	NO	YES

All independent variables are mean centred and lagged by one period. Heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors (clustered at the regional level) are shown in parentheses. Coefficients are statistically significant at the * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$ and *** $p < 0.01$ level.

These results are consistent with the hypothesis and the expected outcomes previously argued. First, the adoption of digital web technologies by regions follows a related diversification kind of process. Second, the adoption of more complex digital web

technologies by regions is associated with productivity gains. Therefore, regions should adopt related digital web technologies, and by doing so, try to increase their digital complexity in order to benefit from the potential productivity gains that may derive from the digital world.

6. Conclusions

Digitalisation has become a clear policy objective. International bodies such as the IMF, WTO, World Bank, and the European Commission have established digitalisation as a crucial target of regional development policies. There are large potential benefits of digitalisation in terms of productivity, employment, and economic growth for European regions. However, the understanding of the diffusion and adoption of digital web technologies for regions remains unclear.

This paper is, to the best of our knowledge, the first in proposing economic complexity and relatedness metrics as a framework to understand digitalisation. First, the digital relatedness density of regions acts as an important driver of the adoption of digital web technologies. Regions tend to adopt new digital web technologies that are related to the ones in which they are already specialised. Second, the digital complexity of regions is found to be positively associated with labour productivity gains at the regional level. This digital complexity may help to explain labour productivity heterogeneity across European regions in a time in which it is the use, and not the access to digital web technologies, that really matters.

Furthermore, this paper has exploited a new source of data based on the use and adoption of digital web technologies by highly innovative firms at a regional level for 278 European regions between the years 2000 and 2022. This data is obtained throughout the *BuiltWith* API. The use of this data presents advantages over other measures of digitalisation. This data is about the real use and adoption of digital web technologies and not about access to the internet, quality of connection or human capital. This data better captures the issues that digitalisation implies nowadays, which are more related to the use of the internet than to the access to the internet.

In this vein, the contributions of the paper are several. First, it applies the relatedness/complexity framework to the adoption of digital web technologies, rather than to the production of such technologies. While previous literature has been focused with the ability of regions to diversify in the production of new technologies and economic activities, much less is known about how such technologies diffuse over time. Second, it proposes a new source of publicly available data to study digitalisation from both a geographical and firm-level perspectives. This contributes to enhancing the set of empirical tools to approach digitalisation dynamics. Third, this paper explores the correlation between the adoption, not production, of digital web technologies and labour productivity at the subnational level. In line with recent studies, the use of complex digital capabilities is associated with economic benefits (Juhász et al. 2024; Stojkoski et al. 2024).

However, this paper is not without limitations. First, due to limitations in the data and empirical setting, no causal claim can be stated. This analysis provides rather descriptive evidence in the interplay between digital web technologies' adoption and labour productivity at the regional level. Second, the use of geo-localised data on firms suffers from a headquarter bias. Nonetheless, the large number of websites operating across regions

makes it difficult to expand the scope of the sample to cover the whole population. Third, the pace of adoption digital web technologies requires continuous updates since it is highly affected by the revolution posed by rising AI technologies. The impact of AI technologies on the digitalisation process of regions is, however, beyond the scope of this paper.

Moreover, the conclusions drawn by this paper have several policy implications. First, digitalisation policies trying to promote the adoption of new and more complex digital web technologies should consider the existing digital capabilities of regions. Regions tend to adopt new digital web technologies when they already master related technologies. In this sense, regions will find it easier to digitally catch-up by adopting related digital web technologies and not trying to achieve the most complex technologies at once. This understanding of digitalisation policies may help regions to avoid lock-ins dynamics and digitalise their economies in a smart way. Furthermore, to acknowledge this can help to break up negative lock-ins scenarios derived from low relatedness density traps (Balland and Boschma 2024; Pinheiro et al. 2022). Thus, regions with lower relatedness density are not condemned to adopt low complex technologies; rather than this, the relatedness/complexity framework allows to assess how selecting complex digital web technologies that are closer in terms of related capabilities could bring higher productivity allowing for obtaining further opportunities.

Second, in the current second era of digitalisation or the digital usage gap, the benefits from digitalisation do not come just from being connected to the digital world. In this sense, the adoption of more complex digital web technologies is positively associated with labour productivity gains. Digitalisation policies should promote the use and adoption of more complex digital web technologies to foster the gains from the digital economy. These policies should integrate other aspects of digitalisation policies such as the promotion of digital skills, to ensure the adoption of more complex technologies and, thus, facilitate the potential productivity gains. Moreover, the timing of the adoption of complex digital web technology is crucial. Regional productivity gains are likely to be more significant during the early stages of adopting complex digital technologies.

Finally, this paper opens a wide range of future research venues. First, the use of application programming interfaces (APIs) such as *BuiltWith* may be a powerful tool to extract publicly available data from web pages. This new source of data may contribute to the empirical understanding of digitalisation dynamics. Second, it is important to dig deeper into the diffusion process of digital web technologies. Especially, the spatial dimension of the interplay between the generation and the adoption of digital web technologies remains understudied. Third, several issues may be influenced by differences in the digital complexity of regions. In this vein, the rise of e-commerce, and its unequal spatial distribution, may be shaped by differences in the adoption of certain digital web technologies.

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Annex

Annex I. List of digital web technologies considered for the analysis

	Tech Group	Tech Category		Tech Group	Tech Category
1	Ads	AD Analytics	51	CDN	CDN
2	Ads	AD Blocking	52	CDNS	CDN
3	Ads	AD Exchange	53	CDNS	CDNS
4	Ads	AD Network	54	CDNS	Edge Delivery Network
5	Ads	AD Server	55	CMS	Agency
6	Ads	ADS TXT	56	CMS	Automotive
7	Ads	ADS	57	CMS	Blog
8	Ads	Adult	58	CMS	CMS
9	Ads	Affiliate Programs	59	CMS	Community CMS
10	Ads	Audience Targeting	60	CMS	Ecommerce Enabled
11	Ads	Bitcoin	61	CMS	Enterprise
12	Ads	Content Curation	62	CMS	Financial
13	Ads	Contextual Advertising	63	CMS	Forum Software
14	Ads	Data Management Platform	64	CMS	Headless
15	Ads	Demand Side Platform	65	CMS	Healthcare
16	Ads	Digital Video ADS	66	CMS	Hosted Solution
17	Ads	Dynamic Creative Optimization	67	CMS	Job Board
18	Ads	Fraud Prevention	68	CMS	Landing Page
19	Ads	Header Bidding	69	CMS	Learning Management System
20	Ads	Local ADS	70	CMS	Mobile
21	Ads	Mobile	71	CMS	Non-Profit
22	Ads	Multi-Channel	72	CMS	Open Source
23	Ads	Retargeting Remarketing	73	CMS	Real State
24	Ads	Search	74	CMS	Simple Website Builder
25	Analytics	AB Testing	75	CMS	Social Management
26	Analytics	Advertiser Tracking	76	CMS	Ticketing System
27	Analytics	Analytics	77	CMS	WIKI
28	Analytics	Application Performance	78	CMS	WIX App
29	Analytics	Audience Measurement	79	Copyright	Copyright
30	Analytics	Call Tracking	80	Encoding	Encoding
31	Analytics	Cart Abandonment	81	Feeds	Feeds
32	Analytics	Conversion Optimization	82	Framework	Framework
33	Analytics	Conversion Tracking	83	Framework	Magento Theme Framework
34	Analytics	CRM	84	Framework	Mobile
35	Analytics	Customer Data Platform	85	Framework	Schema
36	Analytics	Data Management Platform	86	Framework	WordPress Theme
37	Analytics	Error Tracking	87	Hosting	Australian Hosting
38	Analytics	Feedback Forms and Surveys	88	Hosting	Canadian Hosting
39	Analytics	Fraud Prevention	89	Hosting	Chinese Hosting
40	Analytics	Lead Generation	90	Hosting	Cloud Hosting
41	Analytics	Marketing Automation	91	Hosting	Cloud PaaS
42	Analytics	Mobile	92	Hosting	Czech Hosting
43	Analytics	Personalization	93	Hosting	Dedicated Hosting
44	Analytics	Product Recommendations	94	Hosting	Dutch Hosting
45	Analytics	Real State	95	Hosting	Ecommerce Hosting
46	Analytics	Retargeting Remarketing	96	Hosting	French Hosting

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	Tech Group	Tech Category		Tech Group	Tech Category
47	Analytics	Site Optimization	97	Hosting	German Hosting
48	Analytics	Social Management	98	Hosting	Hong-Kong Hosting
49	Analytics	Tag Management	99	Hosting	Hosting
50	Analytics	Visitor Count Tracking	100	Hosting	Italian Hosting
101	Hosting	Japan Hosting	155	Payment	Payments Processor
102	Hosting	Polish Hosting	156	Payment	Payment
103	Hosting	Romanian Hosting	157	Registrar	Registrar
104	Hosting	Russian Hosting	158	Robots	Robots
105	Hosting	Shared Hosting	159	Server	Server
106	Hosting	Spanish Hosting	160	Shipping	Shipping
107	Hosting	Swedish Hosting	161	Shop	Agency
108	Hosting	Swiss Hosting	162	Shop	Automotive
109	Hosting	Turkish Hosting	163	Shop	Enterprise
110	Hosting	UK Hosting	164	Shop	Hosted Solution
111	Hosting	US Hosting	165	Shop	Multi-Channel
112	Hosting	VPS Hosting	166	Shop	Non Platform
113	Hosting	WordPress Hosting	167	Shop	Open Source
114	JavaScript	Animation	168	Shop	Plugin Module
115	JavaScript	Charting	169	Shop	Shipping Provider
116	JavaScript	Compatibility	170	Shop	Shop
117	JavaScript	Framework	171	Shop	Shopify App
118	JavaScript	JavaScript Library	172	Shop	Shopify Theme
119	JavaScript	JavaScript	173	Shop	SMB Solution
120	JavaScript	jQuery Plugin	174	Shop	WooCommerce Extension
121	JavaScript	Slider	175	Shop	WordPress Plugins
122	JavaScript	UI	176	SSL	Extended Validation
123	Language	Language	177	SSL	Root Authority
124	Link	Adult	178	SSL	SSL
125	Link	Link	179	SSL	Wildcard
126	Mapping	Mapping	180	Web Master	Web Master
127	Mapping	Maps	181	Web Server	Web Server
128	Media	Digital Video ADS	182	Web Server	Varnish Server
129	Media	Enterprise	183	Widgets	Bookings
130	Media	Live Stream Webcast	184	Widgets	Bookmarking
131	Media	Media	185	Widgets	Call Tracking
132	Media	Online Video Platform	186	Widgets	Captcha
133	Media	Social Video Platform	187	Widgets	Charting
134	Media	Video Analytics	188	Widgets	Cobrowsing
135	Media	Video Players	189	Widgets	Comment System
136	Mobile	Mobile	190	Widgets	Content Modification
137	MX	Business Email Hosting	191	Widgets	Customer Data Platform
138	MX	Campaign Management	192	Widgets	Ecommerce
139	MX	DMARC	193	Widgets	Error Tracking
140	MX	Marketing Platform	194	Widgets	Feedback Forms and Surveys
141	MX	MX	195	Widgets	Financial
142	MX	Secure Email	196	Widgets	Fonts
143	MX	Transactional Email	197	Widgets	Image Provider
144	MX	Web Hosting Provider Email	198	Widgets	Joomla Module
145	NS	Enterprise DNS	199	Widgets	Live Chat

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	Tech Group	Tech Category		Tech Group	Tech Category
146	NS	NS	200	Widgets	Login
147	NS	TLD Redirects	201	Widgets	Marketing Automation
148	Parked	Parked	202	Widgets	Mobile
149	Payment	Bitcoin	203	Widgets	Privacy Compliance
150	Payment	Checkout Buttons	204	Widgets	Push Notifications
151	Payment	Currency	205	Widgets	Schedule Management
152	Payment	Donation	206	Widgets	Site Search
153	Payment	Pay Later	207	Widgets	Social Sharing
154	Payment	Payment Acceptance	208	Widgets	SSL Seals
209	Widgets	Tag Management	214	Widgets	Web Badge
210	Widgets	Ticketing System	215	Widgets	Widgets
211	Widgets	Tour Site Demo	216	Widgets	WIX App
212	Widgets	Translation	217	Widgets	WordPress Hosting
213	Widgets	VAT Registration	218	Widgets	WordPress Plugins

Annex II. List of European NUTS-tempregions considered for the analysis

AT11	DE25	ES12	HU33	PL22	UKD6
AT12	DE26	ES13	IE04	PL41	UKD7
AT13	DE27	ES21	IE05	PL42	UKE1
AT21	DE30	ES22	IE06	PL43	UKE2
AT22	DE40	ES23	ITC1	PL51	UKE3
AT31	DE50	ES24	ITC2	PL52	UKE4
AT32	DE60	ES30	ITC3	PL61	UKF1
AT33	DE71	ES41	ITC4	PL62	UKF2
AT34	DE72	ES42	ITF1	PL63	UKF3
BE10	DE73	ES43	ITF2	PL71	UKG1
BE21	DE80	ES51	ITF3	PL72	UKG2
BE22	DE91	ES52	ITF4	PL81	UKG3
BE23	DE92	ES53	ITF5	PL82	UKH1
BE24	DE93	ES61	ITF6	PL84	UKH2
BE25	DE94	ES62	ITG1	PL91	UKH3
BE31	DEA1	ES70	ITG2	PL92	UKJ1
BE32	DEA2	FI19	ITH1	PT11	UKJ2
BE33	DEA3	FI1B	ITH2	PT15	UKJ3
BE34	DEA4	FI1C	ITH3	PT16	UKJ4
BE35	DEA5	FI1D	ITH4	PT17	UKK1
BG31	DEB1	FI20	ITH5	PT18	UKK2
BG32	DEB2	FR10	ITI1	PT20	UKK3
BG33	DEB3	FRB0	ITI2	PT30	UKK4
BG34	DEC0	FRC1	ITI3	RO11	UKL1
BG41	DED2	FRC2	ITI4	RO12	UKL2
BG42	DED4	FRD1	LT01	RO21	UKM5
CH01	DED5	FRD2	LT02	RO22	UKM6
CH02	DEE0	FRE1	LU00	RO31	UKNO
CH03	DEF0	FRE2	LV00	RO32	
CH04	DEG0	FRF1	MT00	RO41	
CH05	DK01	FRF2	NL11	RO42	

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CH06	DK02	FRF3	NL12	SE11
CH07	DK03	FRG0	NL13	SE12
CY00	DK04	FRH0	NL21	SE21
CZ01	DK05	FRI1	NL22	SE22
CZ02	EE00	FRI2	NL23	SE23
CZ03	EL30	FRI3	NL31	SE31
CZ04	EL41	FRJ1	NL32	SE32
CZ05	EL42	FRJ2	NL33	SE33
CZ06	EL43	FRK1	NL34	SI03
CZ07	EL51	FRK2	NL41	SI04
CZ08	EL52	FRL0	NL42	SK01
DE11	EL53	FRM0	NO01	SK02
DE12	EL54	HU11	NO02	SK03
DE13	EL61	HU12	NO03	SK04
DE14	EL62	HU21	NO04	UKC1
DE21	EL63	HU22	NO05	UKC2
DE22	EL64	HU23	NO06	UKD1
DE23	EL65	HU31	NO07	UKD3
DE24	ES11	HU32	PL21	UKD4

Annex III. Robustness checks: logit models

	Dependent variable: Entry (=1)			
	(1) Baseline	(2) Controls	(3) Full model	(4) Full model FEs
Constant	-1.752*** (0.00913)	-1.822*** (0.0154)	-1.752*** (0.0102)	
Relatedness density	0.0281*** (0.000869)		0.0300*** (0.000936)	0.0270*** (0.00112)
GDP pc (log)		1.929** (0.858)	-1.163* (0.676)	0.457 (1.183)
Total population (log)		1.713** (0.846)	-0.996 (0.679)	-9.238*** (1.312)
GVA (log)		-1.798** (0.844)	0.920 (0.665)	0.293 (1.152)
Total employment (log)		0.129 (0.124)	-0.0749 (0.0800)	-1.155*** (0.289)
Population density (log)		0.0474*** (0.0161)	0.0159 (0.0113)	7.055*** (1.279)
Patent applications (log)		0.00486 (0.0146)	0.0957*** (0.0113)	0.0810*** (0.0302)
Observations	218,268	218,268	218,268	87,732
Pseudo R-squared	0.02	0.003	0.02	-
Region-Tech FEs	NO	NO	NO	YES
Year FEs	NO	NO	NO	YES

All independent variables are mean centred and lagged by one period. Heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors (clustered at the regional level) are shown in parentheses for all models but the two-way FEs (4). Coefficients are statistically significant at the * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$ and *** $p < 0.01$ level.

Annex IV. Robustness checks: probit models

	Dependent variable: Entry (= 1)		
	(1) Baseline	(2) Controls	(3) Full model
Constant	-1.041*** (0.00492)	-1.083*** (0.00829)	-1.041*** (0.00547)
Relatedness density	0.0155*** (0.000477)		0.0165*** (0.000514)
GDP pc (log)		1.021** (0.464)	-0.671* (0.372)
Total population (log)		0.900** (0.456)	-0.583 (0.374)
GVA (log)		-0.950** (0.456)	0.540 (0.366)
Total employment (log)		0.0755 (0.0665)	-0.0383 (0.0438)
Population density (log)		0.0253*** (0.00865)	0.00808 (0.00620)
Patent applications (log)		0.00212 (0.00797)	0.0512*** (0.00624)
Observations	218,268	218,268	218,268
Pseudo R-squared	0.02	0.003	0.02
Region-Tech FEs	NO	NO	NO
Year FEs	NO	NO	NO

All independent variables are mean centred and lagged by one period. Heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors (clustered at the regional level) are shown in parentheses. Coefficients are statistically significant at the * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$ and *** $p < 0.01$ level.

Annex V. Correlation matrixes

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
(1) Entry	1.000							
(2) Rel_den	0.349	1.000						
(3) GDP_pc	0.052	0.281	1.000					
(4) Tot_pop	0.031	0.163	-0.001	1.000				
(5) GVA	0.045	0.251	0.421	0.835	1.000			
(6) Tot_empl	0.038	0.202	0.117	0.970	0.902	1.000		
(7) Pop_den	0.039	0.192	0.252	0.120	0.213	0.194	1.000	
(8) Patents	0.025	0.119	0.370	0.482	0.722	0.590	0.122	1.000

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
(1) Productivity	1.000						
(2) Complexity	0.133	1.000					
(3) GDP_pc	0.944	0.167	1.000				
(4) Tot_pop	0.030	0.109	0.011	1.000			
(5) Tot_empl	0.101	0.142	0.128	0.971	1.000		
(6) Pop_den	0.161	0.217	0.257	0.117	0.189	1.000	
(7) Patents	0.303	0.091	0.359	0.502	0.606	0.117	1.000

Annex VI. Robustness checks: Spatial productivity models

1. Spatial dependence diagnostic tests:

Test name	Test value	p-value
LMerr	79.5420	<0.001
LMlag	1.7200	0.1897
RLMerr	80.8070	<0.001
RLMlag	2.9847	0.08405
SARMA	82.5270	<0.001

LMerr = Lagrange Multiplier Test for Spatial Error Dependence; LMlag = Lagrange Multiplier Test for Spatial Lag Dependence; RL_Merr = Robust Lagrange Multiplier Test for Spatial Error Dependence; RL_Mlag = Robust Lagrange Multiplier Test for Spatial Lag Dependence; SARMA = Lagrange Multiplier Test for Spatial Autoregressive Moving Average. All coefficients are statistically significant at the following levels: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

2. Empirical model, SARAR Equation with Region and Time Fixed Effects:

$$y_{rt} = \rho W y_{rt} + X_{rt} \beta + \alpha_r + \gamma_t + u_{rt}$$

Where:

- y_{rt} is the dependent variable for region r at time t (y_{rt} represents $\Delta \log(\text{GVA}/E)$)
- ρ is the spatial autoregressive parameter for the dependent variable.
- W is the spatial weights matrix.
- X_{rt} is the matrix of explanatory variables for region r at time t (Digital complexity, GDP per capita, population density).
- β is the vector of coefficients for the explanatory variables.
- α_r represents the region fixed effects, accounting for region-specific unobserved heterogeneity.
- γ_t represents the time fixed effects
- u_{rt} is the spatially autocorrelated error term, modelled as:

$$u_{rt} = \lambda W u_{rt} + \varepsilon_{rt}$$

where:

- λ is the spatial autoregressive parameter for the error term.
- ε_{rt} is the independent and identically distributed error term.
- σ^2 is the variance of the error term.

3. Spatial Productivity models:

Variable	Dependent variable: $\Delta(\log(\text{GVA/E}))$		
	SEM (Model 1)	SARAR (Model 2)	SARAR (Model 3)
(Intercept)	–	–	–
Digital complexity (log)	0.0101* (0.0042)	0.0090* (0.0040)	0.0029 (0.0041)
GDP pc (log)	–0.0092 (0.0160)	0.0003 (0.0163)	0.0573*** (0.0164)
Population density (log)	0.0789 (0.0510)	0.0965* (0.0486)	0.1822*** (0.0533)
Patent applications (log)	–0.0116* (0.0049)	–0.0119* (0.0048)	–0.0218*** (0.0053)
rho	–	–0.2548*** (0.0555)	0.5380*** (0.0660)
delta	0.6917*** (0.0188)	0.7898*** (0.0200)	0.0300 (0.0998)
Observations	1290	1290	1290
Region Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time Fixed Effects	NO	NO	Yes
Sigma	0.0698	0.0700	0.0577
AIC	–6296.22	–6307.15	–6408.21
BIC	–6270.41	–6276.17	–6377.23

All coefficients are statistically significant at the following levels: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$. Standard errors are shown in parentheses. Observations are mean-centred. The dependent variable is the change in labour productivity. The models include region and year fixed effects where indicated. Where SEM-Spatial error model, and SARAR- Spatial autoregressive combined model.